

***Porthetes* sp. nov.**
(ex *Encephalartos horridus*)
Cycad pollination weevil

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Group: Insect

Size: 6-7 mm long

Distribution:

Eastern Cape in the area near Cqeberha and Kariega.

Importance:

Porthetes beetles are pollinators of *Encephalartos* cycads. Both the cycads and weevils have a high extinction risk. Genome sequencing provides a basis for further molecular studies to understand host specificity and options for conserving and recovering pollinator interactions.

PromethION Sequencing Report:

Output: 29.49 Gigabases

Approximate N50: 4.85 kilobases

Draft Genome Assembly Statistics:

Assembler used: Hifiasm

Genome Length: 0.28 Gigabases

BUSCO completeness score: 99.6% [Single: 99.0%, Duplicated: 0.6%]

BUSCO database: insecta

Assembly N50: 21 039 kilobases

Contig number: 507

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